

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPING LITERARY RESEARCH COMPETENCE FOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article is about the importance of developing research competence for high school students. The development of scientific research capacity in the field of literature helps students to be active in learning, nurtures a passion for knowledge. Using summary, observational methods, this study outlines the basic steps that teachers need to guide students when starting a research task. The role of a teacher is not only to impart knowledge but also to light the fire of passion. To develop students' research competence, teachers need to conduct small assignments, study projects, build research plans, write a report in the field of literature. This activity really helps students to develop their quality and competence in scientific research.

Keywords: Development, competence, research, literature, students.

We are living in a century of highly developed intellectual civilization. In this era, science is the foundation of life. Therefore, the development of scientific research is an extremely important activity for high school students in Vietnam. According to Vietnam's education law, the general education method must promote the positivity, self-discipline, initiative and creativity of students in accordance with the characteristics of each grade level, fostering students' self-study methods, practice skills to apply practical knowledge to affect students' emotions and happiness. Scientific research activities in high schools need to be paid more attention to promote creative thinking and put effort into putting knowledge from books into practice, this is a meaningful and necessary thing for students to have can effectively increase knowledge, develop thinking and intellectual capacity to be able to absorb lessons as well as experiences for themselves. There is a great need for a process to guide young people into scientific research, especially exploratory research in the field of literature.

Scientific research is the discovery and development of things and phenomena that have not been found or previously mentioned by science. Therefore, scientific research often has the following characteristics:

Novelty: For a scientific research topic, the most important attribute that is novelty, perhaps the objects of scientific research that are old have already been studied, but we will have to exploit and find out. in a different direction of things, exploiting new aspects that do not duplicate what the previous topic has studied. In the field of literature with many types, genres, authors, works, schools, trends, and trends that predecessors have had works and products, the research orientation to have a better approach is necessary. New approach is absolutely necessary.

Reliability: Before being a scientific research topic, we need to plan specifically for each step,

research is the collection of data results, so any results obtained need to be fully recorded enough evidence, data, and sources of origin so that when we present the research, we must give our opinions and views.

Information: The product of scientific research can exist in many forms such as a scientific article or a scientific report. Whatever form it takes, the results we give must contain certain information.

Objectivity: Science is the process of learning about the nature of things and phenomena, so it needs to be described honestly and objectively.

The purpose of scientific research contributes to improving the quality of training, approaching and applying scientific research methods; solve a number of scientific and practical problems. In developed countries such as the UK, USA, France, Australia, etc, students act as research assistants (Research Assistance) for teachers with research topics. Students who have these experiences can learn and accumulate practical knowledge. Research results will make students firmly grasp the lecture and more confident about what in reality, oftentimes, the teachers themselves need to learn. Vietnamese schools always have activities to honor scientific research results from students. Every year, there are scientific research awards at the school level, the ministerial level, and the young researcher award. That will encourage students to participate in scientific research, create a scientific research movement for students, thereby helping high schools and universities have a research environment and human resources. From the initial habitual manipulations, students acquire research skills and develop into a passion and love to explore literary phenomena, themes and literary works. The development of scientific research capacity helps students to actively, actively and creatively equip themselves with the necessary knowledge to study effectively. Scientific research capacity is a combination of many component competencies, so the

development of scientific research for students will help improve the quality of teaching and develop students' scientific research capacity, which will help shorten gap between general education and higher education. In addition, the development of scientific research capacity for students contributes to the formation and fostering of necessary qualities of knowledge workers, which are diligence, patience to overcome difficulties, curiosity and creativity objectivity and accuracy, know how to apply research results to work and life practice.

The structure of scientific research capacity is the same as any other capacity. Scientific research also needs three main components: knowledge, skills and attitudes. In research we need specialized scientific knowledge; knowledge of scientific research methods. Research planning skills; research topic design skills; data collection skills; critical skills; reasoning skills; scientific report writing skills. In addition, the enthusiastic attitude towards science; sensitive to all things that will happen, persevere, work carefully. Must be objective, enthusiastic, seriously research, skeptical of science, courageously defend scientific truth.

Through scientific research, students' competencies will be developed such as: Ability to detect and solve problems; observation capacity; the ability to read and search for information; thinking capacity; research proposal design capacity; ability to write scientific reports; ability to defend scientific research topics. Among the above competencies, the competencies that can be developed for high school students are: Reading and information searching: The process of reading and searching for documents helps students to recognize problems and find information. raises many research questions. Research thinking capacity includes such as analysis, synthesis, generalization. Developing scientific research for high school students is an extremely important thing, the training of scientific research should be done early, it will contribute to the development of research capacity in general for students. We need to develop a process to help teachers guide students step by step in scientific research more conveniently.

Step 1: The teacher guides students to plan for self - study, self - study, knows how to zone the scope of research activities of the topic.

Make a plan for self - study and self - study to help students' research activities take place in the order that has been arranged according to the plan. Developing a self-study and self-study plan for high school students is a difficult thing, so it needs the support of teachers and teachers can guide them as follows:

Teachers need to clearly state the purpose and importance of scientific research and guide students through the steps involved in developing a research plan. Teachers can guide students to plan according to time, work tasks, regularly check students' plans, make adjustments and additions so that students can correct and complete their own plans me.

Find and narrow down your research topic: Before you begin your research, take a few minutes to set your research goals and develop a clearer idea of the topic. First, write down a few goals for your research.

The setting of research objectives should be carefully considered. If the big goal is not met by the research process, it will be difficult for us to complete. Setting specific goals for the research process will help us stay on the right track and find out new things in the research process do scientific research and have the opportunity to meet and exchange knowledge with those who have gone before to learn about that field. Learn about the topic: Once you've decided on some specific goals, it's time to start working on them, start looking for materials, information, you can actually go and explore the issues related to the topic. Use the internet to enter words related to the topic to be searched, for example, you type "teen inventors" into a search engine. Pick one or two test sites then visit to read your ideas and topics. Talk to the instructor to receive the sharing, research experience. State your research objectives and consult experts.

Step 2: Self - study guide and study materials

The process of reading and collecting materials helps students uncover problems and raise many research questions. For example, when studying folklore, it is necessary to ask questions such as: What are the basic values of folklore? How does folklore affect written literature? How many genres are there in folklore? Do you know any folklore works (fairy tales, myths, epics, poetic stories, folk songs, proverbs...) of ethnic minorities in your locality? Which ethnic group's folklore works do you like to read in the locality where you live? Why? Where can you read (collect, watch through performance) folklore works? In your opinion, what values should be prioritized for promotion? (*cognitive values, educational values, aesthetic values, historical values, religious and philosophical values, cultural values*) ...; Why do you think it is important to preserve and promote the traditional literary values of Vietnam's ethnic minorities? traditional literary values of ethnic minorities?

Asking questions will contribute to the development of students' ability to detect problems. Some activities that teachers can help students with are sending them resources, designing a guide on what to do when entering the research, guiding students to summarize the ideas of the materials and answer the questions. Related questions, for students to search for books and documents for research. For effective reading and understanding of the material, teachers can guide students in the following ways:

When searching for documents:

You need to clearly define the types of documents and topics that need to be included in the topic, identify the "keywords" when searching on the internet to avoid looking up a lot of information that makes it difficult for us to identify identify the main problem. You have to choose the appropriate methods and tools to find valuable documents for your scientific research topic.

Use specific keywords and limit your search

To get the best results from a search, look up a specific, detailed document. Try combining keywords and using search modifiers or limiters, using quotes, separating related words together in quotes, can widen or narrow the search.

When reading the document

The Internet is not the only place to find information. Libraries and resource centers are ideal places to find information. Furthermore, these places provide access to information online. Before you start your research, learn how to organize a library or media center. Most libraries have different sections for adults, youth and children, which have different sections such as business features, local history, culture, literature many libraries and learning centers Is there a quiet space to read books, look up documents? Computer facilities throughout the library give you access to research materials.

When you find the document

You need to carefully read the introduction, summarize the table of contents of the document. You need to clearly define the purpose of finding and reading the material, need to synthesize all the knowledge that you have read that book and need to determine the level of achievement of reading the document. Whether to re - read or seek more information about the research topic.

Step 3: Teachers need to regularly let students do small scientific research projects.

Scientific research is an activity that requires early practice, so teachers need to encourage students to do research through small exercises. This helps them to be active and encourages their love of science. The small topic here is like a simple exercise under the guidance of a teacher, students will have to perform the assigned task with a short time of 2 - 3 days. For example: after studying the fairy tale "Tam Cam", the teacher can give students a topic about the fairy tale genre, including the following issues:

- Talking about good - evil in the fairy tale Tam Cam
- The role of fairy tales in educating people
- Rewrite the ending of the fairy tale Tam Cam from your point of view

Step 4: Have students prepare a part of the lesson and present in front of the class

Many students have the ability to recognize problems and observe thinking very well, but they are not confident enough to stand in front of a crowd to give a presentation. In order to help children have a good ability to speak fluently in front of a crowd, teachers need to give children small projects that encourage them to stand up and speak their ideas, step by step. You will learn how to speak and how to present in front of an audience. This is an extremely important factor in becoming a genuine scientist.

To do this, teachers can follow these steps: Teachers need to deliver the content of a lesson before going to class, need to state the purpose and content requirements of the presentation, divide the class into groups. In groups, teachers publish rubrics to evaluate group products, groups will learn and report research products, collected in the process of finding information. After the groups have finished presenting, students will cross - review and finally the teacher comments and consolidates knowledge after each lesson.

Step 5: Build and use a system of exercises to develop creative thinking

An important thing in scientific research is creative thinking, which is a factor that promotes the formation and development of students' scientific research capacity. Therefore, it is very necessary to build and use a system of exercises and develop creative thinking for students. When solving an exercise, students are trained in thinking operations such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, interpretation...

Requirements of exercises to develop scientific research capacity

- Systematic, logical
- Accurate, scientific
- Exploiting the essential features
- Diversity
- High demands on learners force learners to use

thinking methods competently.

Step 6: Increase the use of teaching methods capable of helping students develop scientific research capacity

In order to develop scientific research for students, in addition to using traditional teaching methods such as presentations and conversations, teachers need to actively use advanced teaching methods such as research methods and methods raise problems, project teaching methods ...

Research method: This method is very effective in promoting self - reliance, active creativity of students. The teacher acts as an organizational guide and the students discover and solve problems on their own, which helps students to think independently, so the acquisition of knowledge is very solid.

Problem raising method: Is a combination of complex teaching methods, a set of many closely linked teaching methods.

Case teaching method: in this method, teachers provide students with teaching situations for students to learn, analyze and act in situations, which helps learners acquire knowledge and attitudes degree and skill of action after solving the given situation. This method is very effective in training students' problem-solving ability.

Project teaching method: this is a good form of teaching, under the guidance of teachers, students acquire knowledge and form skills through solving some real-life situations. live, follow the curriculum, combine theory with practice to create specific products. This teaching method helps to develop skills of teamwork, experimenting with finding documents, writing scientific reports, etc.

Organize research activities.

- Write the opening paragraph:

Starting with a topic sentence that suggests research questions, you need to state why you chose this research topic. This is a good way to arouse interest in the reader and the first sentences need to clearly state the content of the scientific research topic.

For example: The topic "Developing literary research capacity for high school students" we need to write an introduction in three steps:

Step 1: State the reason for choosing the problem: Outline the nature, position and importance of the research problem.

Step 2: Outline the current situation of the research problem

Step 3: Pedagogical experiment.

Consider using keywords.

When writing a scientific research topic, before entering the research paper, you should convention keywords to help readers quickly identify the research area you are aiming for.

- Writing the body:

Depending on the overall length of the paper, the introduction should provide an overview of published research in the same field. This is important because it shows your deep knowledge and understanding of the research and debate in your area of expertise.

The introduction should show that despite your broad knowledge, you will be focusing on the issues that are most relevant to your research. It is necessary to write concisely and concisely to go straight to the main issue, to provide an overview of the whole topic, to avoid rambling on the wrong focus and to highlight the importance of research activities. Through the theoretical basis, clarify your contribution. A concise yet comprehensive piece of theoretical background can be an effective way to shape research. As you develop your introduction, you can go from theory to key research and its own niche in the field.

❖ By explicitly referencing existing works, you can show specific contributions to the overall development of your area of expertise.

❖ Can you identify gaps in current research and explain how you approach and promote knowledge development.

Explain in detail the reason for the study. Once you have identified the specific niche of your work, you can more fully explain the rationale for the study, its strengths, and its own importance. This rationale should be stated clearly and succinctly, showing the value of the research as well as the contribution to the field of study. Emphasize the positive contributions of the work.

❖ For example, if you are writing scientific research, you can emphasize the value of the empirical model or method used.

❖ Emphasize the novelty of your research and the importance of your new approach. Don't go into too much detail in the introduction, though.

- Write a conclusion

You need to present your idea, or topic sentence, in a clear and concise manner. It shows that the research paper will make a specific contribution and have clear results, not just cover a general topic. You should clarify how you came to this hypothesis and refer to the theoretical basis. With scientific texts, clearly stating the results obtained and their relationship to hypotheses in just a few sentences makes the information clear and accessible.

Outline the research paper. In some cases, the last part of the introduction will be a few lines presenting an overview of the content structure of the research paper. You can simply present your outline and how you organize and break down your writing. This is not always necessary. You should be aware of the practices used when writing research in your field. Often the

humanities and social sciences courses can be more flexible in structure.

- *How to present references.* It is very important to cite and list references in the essay. If you use someone else's work, you need to cite the author and source. When using unreliable documents in the article, questions should be raised about whether they are reliable to cite? The case of not clearly indicating the source of the quotation of another person's words or sentences is the phenomenon of plagiarism whether intentionally or unintentionally. Writing citations required in the thesis is to write the source of the citation right in the content of the article and list the references at the end of the research paper. The citation of references not only shows respect for the author's copyright, but also shows the depth and seriousness of the research. Therefore, citations and references must be properly presented.

Scientific research for high school students does not require superiority or stature. The main goal of scientific research is to equip students with knowledge and skills for independent scientific research to support their learning activities, and to prepare students with knowledge and skills when doing research enter universities. Scientific research activities in the field of literature of students have many different forms such as writing essays, making reports, doing research projects. These studies will bring practical meaning for students in discovering and understanding authors and works.

Scientific research helps students to supplement the knowledge not learned in the regular program, to fill the knowledge about social life to enrich their own living capital. When the research topic refers to the reality, there is a practical survey that helps students understand more deeply about things that are not only taught in theory in the classroom. Scientific research will help students deepen the knowledge they have learned, develop the ability to analyze, evaluate, associate and combine new things to solve unanswered problems.

And from one problem will expand to many problems that enrich students' knowledge. The fact that research will help students have experience writing reports, these experiences are really necessary when studying in a university program. At the same time, scientific research activities help students to have the ability to think creatively, to criticize, to refute or to prove a certain point of view knowledge, logical thinking and mutual help. Science and technology affect almost every aspect of our lives, the power of scientific research exposes students to new things, stimulates creativity and the ability to work independently student's.

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НЕКРАСОВСКИЙ ВЧЕРАШНИЙ ДЕНЬ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ И АРМЯНСКОМ

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NEKRASOV'S YESTERDAY AT SIX IN ENGLISH AND ARMENIAN

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается перевод стихотворения Николая Некрасова «Вчерашний день, часу в шестом» на английский (Брайан Рид) и на армянский (Ав. Исаакян – С. Таронци) языки. Проводится сравнительно-сопоставительный анализ композиции, строфики, ритмо-рифмического построения, а также переводов на армянский и английский языки, уделяется особое внимание одному из ключевых понятий в процессе перевода, проблеме эквивалентности.

В статье рассматриваются лексика и фонетика, грамматические формы, рифма и рифмовка, чтобы показать, насколько адекватны переводы и какие изменения претерпел оригинал.

Abstract

The article deals with the translation of Nikolay Nekrasov's poem «Yesterday at six» into English (Brian Reed) and Armenian (Av. Isahakyan – S. Tarontsi). A comparative examination of the composition of the poem, its stanza division, rhyme construction, as well as their translations into Armenian and English, paying a special attention to one of the key concepts in the translation process, the problem of equivalence is carried out.

In the article the lexics and phonetics, grammar and form, rhyme and rhythm will be studied to show how adequate the translations are and what changes the original underwent.

Ключевые слова: «Вчерашний день, часу в шестом», Брайан Рид, Ав. Исаакян, С. Таронци, Некрасов, перевод, сравнение, строфа, композиция, структура, рифма, четверостишие, сравнительный анализ, эквивалентность.

Keywords: «Yesterday at six», Brian Reed, Av. Isahakyan, S. Tarontsi, Nekrasov, translation, comparison, stanza, composition, structure, rhyme, quatrain, comparative analysis, equivalence.